

TalX Workshop 4: The role of Communities in developing Place-Based Adaptation

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Introduction

A changing climate poses a wide range of impacts and risks for society in Britain and Ireland. To prepare for the impacts of climate change, effective and sustainable adaptation action is needed on a cross-sectoral and multi-level basis. This needs to be underpinned by an increase in the capacity of organisations and communities to deliver adaptation actions in different places across Britain and Ireland.

As part of the EPA-funded Transboundary Adaptation Learning Exchange (TalX) project, an adaptation Capability and Maturity Model (CMM) is being created for the five jurisdictions of Britain and Ireland (Republic of Ireland, Northern Ireland, Scotland, Wales and England). This model will provide a mechanism to enable place-based adaptation through the provision of a structured change process, illustrating the development of adaptation capabilities for all stakeholders acting in a place. This includes all members of the community from major public sector organisations, to local businesses and community groups. The adaptation CMM will also enable the integration of bottom-up and top-down priorities and actions, mainstreaming adaptation into all considerations of the area to best meet the needs of place-based adaptation.

To develop the CMM a series of co-creation workshops are being held online that invite experienced adaptation practitioners and policymakers from across the Britain and Ireland to provide their insights and experiences of ‘on the ground’ adaptation and the capabilities required to deliver it effectively. The first of these workshops (practitioner perspectives on well-adapting places) was held on March 29th and 30th and invited practitioners from across the jurisdictions to identify priority capability themes for inclusion in the CMM. The priority capability themes identified included:

- Leadership and Ownership (**Leadership**)
- Research, Knowledge and Expertise (**Evidence**)
- Community Education, Engagement, Involvement and Empowerment (**Community**)
- Collaboration, Cross-Sectoral Networks and Partnerships (**Partnerships**)
- Sustained and Secure Funding and Resource (**Resource**)

For each priority theme, a dedicated workshop is being held (Figure 1) to explore that theme in detail.

Figure 1: Themes in the Workshop Series with the theme of this workshop (Community) report outlined in red

Workshop 4 - Community

The fourth TalX workshop was held on the 2nd of September 2021 and examined the priority theme 'Community'. The workshop aimed to establish the role of communities in place-based adaptation, the need for engagement with communities, the leadership provided by communities and the actions and activities necessary to develop this. The workshop was targeted at experienced climate adaptation practitioners from across the 5 jurisdiction areas (Appendix 1).

There are many definitions of what constitutes a community in place-based adaptation. For the purposes of this workshop community is defined as including '*all peoples and organisations connected to a place*'.

The purpose of the workshop was to draw out the role that communities currently play in place-based adaptation decision-making and action. The workshops explored the role, benefits and challenges of community involvement in place-based adaptation. Participants shared stories of their own experiences and also identified specific actions that enable community involvement to develop over time.

Workshop Structure

To support workshop activities and prior to the workshop, a [pre-recorded video](#) was circulated to all participants which provides an overview of the TalX project (Appendix 2). The workshop was delivered online over one afternoon and included two introductory presentations and two work sessions (WS) (Figure 2).

Introductory Presentations:

The introductory presentations provided an overview of the role of local communities in advancing place-based climate adaptation and how adaptation action is more effective and successful when community knowledge and insight is involved from the beginning. These presentations set the scene for the subsequent work sessions and the discussions around the role of communities in climate adaptation.

The first speaker, Marek Soanes, a researcher at the International Institute for Environment and Development (IIED), presented on locally led adaptation initiatives in the Global South. He discussed what locally led action is, why it is needed and the principles used to ensure that locally led adaptation is not only successful but also just, inclusive, transparent and sustainable on a global level.

Following this, Alex Cameron-Smith, the community and climate change engagement coordinator from the Pembrokeshire Coastal Forum in Wales presented on the lessons learned at a local level in climate adaptation engagement in Pembrokeshire, including the importance of approaching local leaders first to ensure their support, a locally focussed dataset and the need for blended learning techniques (e.g. using different types of instructional material for in-person and digital engagement) to reach a wider audience.

Work Sessions:

The work sessions focused on the need for community involvement in place-based climate adaptation, identifying case studies from across Britain and Ireland where communities are involved in adaptation

and examining actions that can be taken to increase the capacity of communities to play a role in adaptation in their 'place' (Figure 2).

Work Session 1: The role, benefits and challenges of community involvement in place-based adaptation

WS1 explored the role of community in place-based adaptation and identified the benefits and challenges in involving community in place-based adaptation. This was achieved through a structured exercise employing Miro to identify and examine the stories of adaptation from different places, discussions in break-out rooms around the lessons learned, and a plenary discussion outlining the main findings of each group from the break-out rooms.

Work Session 2: The actions to support the development of community involvement in place-based adaptation

WS2 involved two inter-related tasks. The first task encouraged participants to think about what approaches (actions, resources and guidance) they have used with or as part of a community to help them support adaptation. The second task examined how these approaches have evolved over time as adaptation progresses. Both tasks were carried out using Miro, alongside discussions in breakout groups and employed structured information gathering and maturity mapping exercises. Following this the key findings from each break out room were outlined in plenary.

Figure 2: An illustration showing the layout of the work sessions

Results

The presentations on community addressed various aspects, opportunities and challenges of community involvement faced by practitioners in different locations and at different stages of adaptation development. The work sessions were coordinated via Miro, where the outputs of the working sessions are stored. They are available at: [TaIX Workshop September 02nd, Online Whiteboard for Visual Collaboration](#) (miro.com). The insights and outputs for each of these are summarised below:

Work Session 1 – Stories on the benefits and challenges of community involvement in adaptation

WS1 highlighted the benefits and challenges of community involvement in adaptation through case studies and examples of success and failure. These have been grouped thematically for ease of understanding and to avoid duplication. There were 10 themes identified (Appendix 3) in exercise 1 which asked participants to identify the benefits and challenges of communities having an equitable stake in place-based adaptation. These were:

- Communication and Engagement;
- Expectations;
- Local evidence, Lived Knowledge and Experience;
- Resources;
- Practicalities;
- Collaboration;
- Holistic Vision of Place;
- Trust;
- Topic Focus and
- Ownership and Local Politics.

In exercise 2, which asked participants to outline community success stories and lessons learned, five themes were identified (Appendix 4); these were Leadership, Engagement, Communication, Resources and Holistic Approach.

Of the themes identified in exercise 1 the themes of Communication and Engagement and Ownership and Local Politics were the areas that participants considered the most challenging. In the theme of Holistic Vision of Place no challenges were identified, whereas in the themes of Topic Focus, Resources and Practicalities no benefits were identified. The themes of Expectations, Local evidence, Lived Knowledge and Experience, Collaboration and Trust all had a relatively equal number of benefits and challenges identified.

The number of points provided under the themes of Communication and Engagement and Ownership and Local Politics suggests that these may be the themes which participants engage with most, and might indicate that the participants or communities consider these themes necessary to address for place-based adaptation. In particular the focus on the importance of a good communication strategy when engaging with communities and the need for fair and equitable representation from the community in decision-making processes, suggests that these are topics that all regions in Britain and Ireland feel need to be addressed for effective climate adaptation. The lack of benefits identified under certain themes, in particular resource, may suggest that this is something that needs to be addressed at a national level for involving communities in place-based adaptation.

Exercise 2 focused more on specific case studies and examples from the participants, where traits, actions, resources or tools were employed in community adaptation. Of the five themes identified there was a greater number of success stories than lessons to learn identified by participants in the themes of Engagement, Communication, Resources and Holistic Approach, and an equal number in Leadership. In Engagement a major focus was the need to map out specific stakeholders to first build trust and to help bring in a wider audience. In Communication, key points identified as necessary for successful community involvement included; employing co-creation techniques, using visual tools and focusing on local narratives. Under the theme of Resources the participants identified using funding wisely and identified long-term planning that builds on lived experience as important, while under Holistic Approach the key focus was on using existing community spirit and bonds and understanding the need for social change alongside climate adaptation. Under the theme of Leadership, persistence and authentic leadership were identified as important for success.

Work Session 2 – Actions/Resources/Guidance to develop community involvement in adaptation

WS2 identified the actions, resources and guidance that participants had used with, or as part of, a community to develop/progress place based adaptation and involved a maturity mapping exercise discussing how the actions, resources and guidance identified throughout the workshop evolve over time in place-based adaptation.

In terms of activities, there were four key themes that the participants felt had helped them develop community involvement in climate adaptation (Appendix 5), these activities have been classified as relating to:

- Communication and Engagement;
- Collaboration and Learning;
- Resource; and
- Motivation and Sustained Involvement.

There was some overlap in WS1 and WS2, with many of the actions identified in WS2 building on the themes identified from the stories of place-based adaptation highlighted in WS1, particularly those related to Communication and Engagement and Collaboration and Learning.

The maturity mapping exercise discussed how actions to involve the community identified earlier in WS2 evolve over time. Each group discussed the actions, resources and guidance that they felt helped them develop community involvement in their adaptation journey from those places just starting out, right through to a mature well-adapted place, ‘implementing on the ground’ action (Appendix 6).

Stages of maturity for community involvement in climate adaptation have been split into 4 different levels which are described below:

Level 1

Community involvement that educates and creates safe, open spaces for learning. Those working in climate adaptation promote visioning exercises for place-based adaptation while also managing expectations.

Level 2

The community is engaged in climate adaptation with a strong vision, democratic processes and structures of working, communities have identified co-benefit opportunities that are funded and supported by government.

Level 3

Community climate champions drive change and entire communities are part of the decision-making process for adaptation solutions, informed by locally relevant and scale related appropriate data.

Level 4

Communities are fully involved in place-based adaptation and engaging with national priorities, with a constant cycle of evaluated actions and iterations. Learning networks are transboundary and intergenerational, supporting self-sustaining proactive adaptation.

To progress through each of these stages, different activities to support community involvement have been identified as necessary at each level.

Level 1

Activities: At this stage in adaptation, practitioners need to work with communities to create safe open spaces for learning and use these to promote education on what adaptation is and encourage collective visioning. By using a local or nearby climate event, practitioners can invite speakers that have personal experience of the effects of climate change to provide case studies and highlight risks that the community may not have been aware of. These spaces also provide an opportunity to build relationships and trust with the community ‘gatekeepers’ who can help ensure all of the community is represented in any decision-making. The community need to be made aware of the limitations of plans and actions that can be implemented locally so that they have realistic expectations of adaptation and timeframes for change, however running smaller pilot projects, especially those that can tie in with other initiatives in the community, can build confidence and help generate useful feedback.

Figure 3: Specific actions for those fostering community involvement in the beginning stage of adaptation

Level 2

Activities: By this stage, communities are more aware of the risks they are facing and practitioners can make communities aware of special features in their 'place' to promote pride of place and increase their willingness to engage with adaptation. Tailoring the evidence and showcasing published examples can promote a common-sense approach to land management and use and explore the co-benefits of adaptation. By employing stakeholder mapping within communities, identifying the key people that need to be involved and consulting with representative groups (going to them if they can't come to you), practitioners can identify what they care about and begin to learn from the community, while also using this opportunity to steer solutions towards those that are already supported by government and are more likely to receive funding. Initiating smaller projects and linking their outputs can build the profile of adaptation while also building trust with the community. Acknowledging the efforts of those involved in these adaptation actions is also important in order for the community members to feel that their input adds value to adaptation initiatives. Practitioners must be consistent when engaging with the community and communicate clearly and honestly to avoid unrealistic expectations, especially around the democratic processes and structures of working. Overall communities at this stage of adaptation should be considering the next steps in their place-based adaptation vision and reflecting on what they have learned already, while also avoiding knee-jerk reactions that could cause maladaptation.

Figure 4: Specific actions for those fostering community involvement in a developing stage of adaptation

Level 3

Activities: By this stage of adaptation the community should have developed a local-scale evidence base and data and information on the impacts of climate change within the place should be available and understood on a granular local level, as should information on the policies and decision-making (e.g. building standards and land management and use) that will affect any adaptation actions. The scale of the place (rural versus urban) and the existing structures and processes that are used also need to be understood by practitioners and utilised properly to build a sense of community within the place and secure wider buy-in. Communities at this stage of adaptation should begin to have local champions driving change, with more official support from government in the background. This local ownership will encourage community organisations and businesses to engage with adaptation action and grow knowledge sharing networks, with peer learning central. This increase in knowledge and involvement will also allow for joint adaptation funding applications and increased resources that have co-benefits for multiple stakeholders within the community.

Figure 5: Specific actions for those fostering community involvement in a relatively robust stage of adaptation

Level 4

Activities: At this stage of adaptation there should be an established level of trust and respect at all levels between stakeholders, with continuous support from central government but with community leadership and strong community involvement. Actions should be larger scale, with multi-level and multi-actor partnerships and using co-operative models which allow for meaningful change. Crisis events such as the global pandemic can be capitalised on to mobilise responses to climate action as stakeholders are aware of what is possible. Practitioners and communities working together can maintain a constant cycle of adaptation projects and iterations, and avail of funding opportunities, especially those that can leverage money using a national ‘hook’ for adaptation actions. Communication at this stage of adaptation needs to be clear and honest with continual evaluation of what is working well in the place and what isn’t. Practitioners should also encourage disruptive innovation and local knowledge and scientific data should be considered equally in decision-making. By highlighting the lived experiences of the community and passing learning on through storytelling intergenerational and transboundary adaptation can be promoted, allowing for less reactive actions and a move towards climate proofing. Growing the community involvement will also help develop self-sustaining processes and keep adaptation networks increasing and strengthening over time.

Figure 6: Specific actions for those fostering community involvement in the mature stage of adaptation

Conclusions

The workshop helped draw out insights and information on community involvement from the experiences of the participants/adaptation practitioners across different places in Britain and Ireland. In doing so, the workshop identified the challenges faced by involving communities equitably in adaptation planning and actions.

The workshop highlighted that involving communities in adaptation and acknowledging their lived experiences and insights into the problems facing the place is key. Participants outlined the importance of clear and honest communication with communities, particularly through the use of interactive tools, visual materials and storytelling narratives. The use of these tools was found to be effective to both those beginning adaptation initiatives and those at more advanced stages of adaptation.

Successful place-based adaptation is seen as a multi-actor process that needs community involvement, the inputs of adaptation practitioners and the support of government. Place-based adaptation needs to be closely aligned with the social and economic values of a place and to do this there needs to be representative input into the decision-making from all groups within the community. This involves a level of trust between the different stakeholders and a culture of support, both internally and externally.

Overall the participants emphasized that adaptation that uses this co-production process with communities, starting from the beginning of any adaptation planning, and taking on board what members of the community see as essential to their 'place', will have the greatest level of engagement and support and will be most effective.

The TalX team would like to thank all the attendees and especially the speakers, for their active participation and willingness to share their insights and experience in order to promote and enable climate adaptation actions in Britain and Ireland.

Appendix 1: Participant list for the Community workshop

Workshop 4- Community		
Participant	Country - Organisation	Country
Martha Farrell	The Maharees Conservation Association	Ireland
Laura Dixon	Mayo County Council	Ireland
Christine Baker	Fingal County Council	Ireland
Sabrina Dekker	Dublin City County Council	Ireland
Hans Visser	Fingal County Council	Ireland
Caroline Corrigan	Meath County Council	Ireland
Eugene Farrell	National University of Ireland, Galway (NUIG)	Ireland
Alex Cameron-Smith	Pembrokeshire Coastal Forum	Wales
Andrew Thomas	Aberystwyth University	Wales
Marek Soanes	International Institute for Environment and Development	England
Eirini Gallou	Historic England	England
Robyn Pender	Historic England	England
Naomi Clarke	Dundee City Council	Scotland
Emma Whitham	Project Manager of Highland Adapts	Scotland
Eleanor Pratt	Sniffer	Scotland
Catherine Payne	Sniffer	Scotland
Cornell Hamxomphou	Cemvo Scotland	Scotland
Emma Adair	Ards and North Down Bourough Council	Northern Ireland
John Barry	Queens University Belfast	Northern Ireland
James Convery	DEARA	Northern Ireland
Perla Mansour	Climate Northern Ireland	Northern Ireland
Cathy Burns	Derry City and Strabane District Council	Northern Ireland
Amy Bell	Climate Northern Ireland	Northern Ireland

Appendix 2: Workshop Agenda

Agenda for the Talx Community Workshop 14:00-16:30 2nd September 2021

Background

As part of the Irish EPA funded Transboundary Adaptation Learning Exchange (TalX - www.Talx.ie) project we are developing a Capability Maturity Model (CMM) to help progress climate adaptation across the UK and Ireland (taking action to prepare for and adjust to both the current effects of climate change and the predicted impacts in the future). The CMM aims to support adaptation practitioners across the UK and Ireland in advancing planning for, and implementation of, effective place-based adaptation.

Following on from the initial workshop exploring practitioner perspectives on well-adapting places, 5 are a priority for advancing effective place-based adaptation and we will be holding a series of workshops exploring these capabilities in detail.

Select Practitioners from across the UK and Ireland are invited so we hope it will be a useful learning and sharing process for all involved and will contribute towards building a stronger climate adaptation network.

This workshop will focus on the role of communities in relation to place-based adaptation when and how.

Useful Information:

- In advance of the workshop and to make the most efficient use of time available, participants are asked to view a video presentation providing an overview of the TalX project. The video presentation has been made available [here](#)
- To support workshop activities, MIRO and Mentimeter platforms will be used. We recommend that you familiarise yourself with these tools prior to the workshop so that you can get the most out of the sessions. You can find a short introductory video on how to use Miro [here](#) and Mentimeter [here](#)

Access to the Workshop:

The workshop will be held online and through Microsoft Teams, the following link can be used to access the workshop [here](#)

Time	Title	Topic	Presenter
14:00	Welcome and Project Overview	Overview of the aims and agenda of the workshop	Barry O'Dwyer & Jade Berman
14:15	Key Note Speakers	Marek Soanes – International Institute for Environment and Development - (Locally Led Adaptation Principles) Title TBC Alex Cameron-Smith – Pembrokeshire Coastal Forum - Coastal Communities Adapting Together (CCAT) Title TBC	Marek Soanes Alex Cameron-Smith
14:40	Work session 1	Interactive discussions and exercises to explore the role of community in place-based adaptation sharing stories of best and not so best practice to learn together...	All
15:10	Break		
15:15	Work session 2	Interactive discussions and exercises to explore how the role of communities changes at different stages on the journey towards a well adapting place and what actions, tools and resources have most impact.	All
16:20	Wrap Up and Close	Summary of the workshop outputs	TalX Team

Appendix 3: WS1-Task 1-What are Benefits and Challenges of Communities having an equitable stake in PBA?

Community Theme	Benefits	Challenges
Communication and Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It's important to show co-benefits when presenting adaptation outcomes to the community to create buy-in Equitable community involvement enables communication between levels of decision making (eg local to regional) to help alignment of strategies Having open and honest discussions about climate change impacts, without judgement on vulnerabilities, is important. Peer to peer learning can be very effective (Locals can contribute with stories)- It might be that the first change locals have to hear about is from each other (eg the poor woman who found that her house - the only one in the village to flood - had been built on the local pond) before they can fully buy-in to climate adaptation Empowerment and confidence to act more independently in the future will ensure buy-in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There can be a lack of understanding of the actual effects of climate change and therefore what adaptation is needed within communities A good communication plan is essential. Present technical and scientific information in an easily understood and accessible format that all participants understand, including building people's vocabulary to allow them to participate with other decision makers Community still does not have the status it needs to have. Giving space for difficult old and new emotions about past and future impacts How are difficult decisions presented and justified? - The messages can be shocking or unwelcome – (e.g. if coastal abandonment is the only option) Finding the right means of engagement at the right time - when more informal spaces are necessary Digital exclusions need to be considered when communicating information Genuine engagement - that includes and values all aspects of community is resource intensive and takes time Getting and maintaining buy-in from the local community (Convincing people to spend time getting involved in this process) The role of Councilors can be disruptive to buy-in Many important people in communities (i.e. those who often don't have a voice) will take some time and support to get used to how to take effective part in consultations
Expectations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Important to showcase the 'do nothing' option and other scenarios 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Managing expectations - setting boundaries for what is possible and what people expect
Local evidence, Lived Knowledge and Understanding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local knowledge provides deeper richer insights on climate hazards and impacts (particularly intersecting/interconnecting ones) and can provide specific recommendations to adapt. Their knowledge of the area, the people, the relationships, the issues, and solutions, through lived experience needs to be valued People may have more knowledge than they realize: but need the right environment to unlock that knowledge. Especially, of course, if it contradicts received opinion. Experts and communities need to learn from each other through knowledge exchange (the Roundtree/ Collingwood work for Defra on local flood groups: the EA was shocked to find that local people often knew a great deal more about the causes of problems, and therefore their potential solutions). Insight into the past or local change through storytelling and sharing experiences Communities want to be heard, offering a space for their traditional knowledge to be shared will empower communities Understanding the change that is occurring within places first through the use of tools such as historic maps, before taking into account the need for action is necessary 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Education may be needed to get people up speed: for example, the reasons for building-level problems may be misunderstood by owners and occupiers - and indeed a lot of the advice out there is poor, or at best difficult to understand. This makes community stakeholders feel confused and powerless. Break down myths and make sure people feel local knowledge is relevant and considered equally in decisions - Focus on experiential knowledge from past events Local communities sometimes don't know who to ask/come to for support even when they want to take action Monitoring and evaluating- challenge: ability to break norms, and continuously upgrade
Resources		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Funding

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adequate resources & capacity for meaningful engagement and participation • Skills, awareness, easier for large, well established stakeholders, delivering benefits that fits different community groups needs and have them support climate adaptation actions • Finance and knowledge of governance - unless there is an established entity (in Ireland at least) - funding options will be limited and in our experience, our funded projects precipitated others and had a positive snowball effect) - if we had not set up as a company, we would not have been as successful - however, it costs in the region of 1500 euros in Ireland if you include insurance and accountancy fees etc. pa - this is off putting.
Practicalities		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How are communities rewarded for their input? – are their efforts recognized? • Lack of organisation across different local groups • National lockdowns make engagement difficult • How to work with under 18s? (safeguarding issues) • People have other priorities - Do people (communities and citizens) actually have the time and energy to be as involved as we need them to be?
Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greater collaboration between and across communities • More collaboration at a local level • Sometimes communities and community groups can intervene to support community members (e.g. in a crisis situation) when agencies cannot or will not. Community groups/ communities are willing to do the extraordinary because of bonds formed during community work • Synergies to protect natural and cultural assets that matter to communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Massive transformation in Ireland required to support coastal communities in Ireland with a Natura 2000 site and a high tourism input - zero enforcement or coastal management means members of coastal communities are pitted against visitors and each other - due to very poor awareness of the role and importance of sand dune systems - so wild camping, fires etc. continue to degrade these vital disappearing and vulnerable coastal habitats and defences
Holistic vision of place	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Just transition • Holistic view of what a place means to the community • Can prove/find additionality ie. that climate adaptation can have many positive benefits for the community eg. NBS increase biodiversity, health etc. • Creating a sense of hope • Better engagement in the future • Creation of sustainable adaptation solutions • Use traditional practices to promote holistic/ sustainable ways of living (from building to protecting natural resources) 	
Trust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working with trusted community members will aid buy-in for adaptation projects • Building trust is very important need major organisations to be willing to value lived experience and actively involve community members in place based adaptation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor relationships with local authorities can interfere with adaptation initiatives • Local authorities may not be trusted to lead on adaptation • Managing consultation fatigue and building trust that sustained engagement involvement and action will continue
Topic Focus		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate change is a multiplier - it will often bring to the fore more general dissatisfactions, making it difficult to concentrate on adaptation issues • Keeping discussions focused on adaptation (and not mitigation etc.) can be a challenge
Ownership and Local politics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wider ownership allows more capacity for action • Previous work in the area can help us understand local power dynamics and sensitivities that need to be understood • Opportunities for local empowerment in decision-making • The role of Councilors can be an aid • Authentic voices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exclusion reinforced at the local level, local political economies and power struggles are just as important as regional/national level politics • Requires decentralised resources, power & skills - negative impacts of austerity? • NI has local and central government so communities are torn on who controls what • Local control/permissions required/red tape can be a huge barrier • Difficult to get a representative community group

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptation can unite communities in a common purpose - particularly in a post conflict society • Making sure you get the right stakeholders - not just people already engaged in climate change • Forums and places that are accessible for everyone and accounting for who takes part to avoid exclusion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal politics within communities can cause challenges and promote exclusion • Can be difficult to reach underrepresented groups - Accessibility in terms of transport and broadband etc can be an issue • Risk that not all voices will be heard equitably - some local actors may dominate • Representative diversity in those who engage; diversity in attitudes, ideas, knowledge, demographics – we need new forms of democratisation
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Appendix 5: Summary of WS1-Task 2 results: Community Impact stories for thriving adapting places

Theme	Successful	Lessons to Learn
Leadership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Having leaders with personalities aligned to community leadership helps. https://online.jwu.edu/blog/MBA-personality-traits-effective-leaders Persistence to keep sustained efforts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Don't undermine community groups - give them tools to do it themselves. Teach them how as much as possible don't do it for them. Sometimes the community group has the solution. Lessons learned: Ireland lacks policy to protect our dune habitats. Visitor management and a multi-agency response are key!
Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Outreach - talk and present at and attend every event because you'll build your network and find support and help. Engage the schools, unis, other community groups as much as possible Orkney island - engaging with people to understand locally. Employed a range of snowballing sampling approaches to cover all people considered Find that putting on something that is more than just a chat is beneficial - using films, having food, then chat to follow - need things to entice people along Harvest Festival Working through peers - who are the influencers with your community? Youth parliament or youth convenor Fingal Council - from local authority perspective public meetings most common way, key thing is to always engage from the start Map out the specific stakeholders for engagement Have staff in place to engage and build relationships with the community Outer Hebrides - Very connected to the land and the change of seasons and they want longer term climate planning and locally specific information Bring in the help of academics - the authorities listen to them to a greater degree SDGs - Urbact - to get to the right people, worked with social scientist to understand how to approach hard to reach people - identify and access the those who are trusted/ gatekeepers Bertrow - need to get all stakeholders, need to have leads within the communities. Community Visioning (Mayo) - engaged with hard to reach towns. Stories that identify the positives - Community Futures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Risks are less direct in developed areas, (with the exception of flooding) - climate risk means different things to different areas – so adapt to your audience Focus on climate rather than weather information needs to be introduced Engagement typically representative over >30, younger people schools, however now younger pops more knowledgeable - need to capture them - not seen good examples to capture them Hidden Voices example project Climate data relatively long term - difficult to get engagement going - if you don't start showing action you lose community
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In my experience we are visual thinkers, and the other great tool on top of images is similar: case studies. But more and more I am feeling this is as much about giving people the information to unlock their own voices, which we than need to hear. Use information in a way that will culturally resonate with the community - art/music etc Co-creation and two-way input - Learn to listen as well as speaking Need specific stories people can relate back to Use projections of technical data into useful narratives for local use in adaptation Practical information that is relevant to the people involved Native Gaelic speakers - use appropriate language in areas that culturally use other languages Need to use contexts and examples specific to the place Communicating as much as possible using different media. - success stories - our dune recovery photos got us a lot of buy in. raising the profile of our natural heritage created pride in the protected species and in turn helped to change behaviour 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication means two-way: words like "risk assessment", "climate projections" can imply one way (Heard as: "We've gathered you here to GIVE you information, not receive it") Our reliance on words is a problem: Even professions seem actually to 'see' more if you show than the right image. At least that's what I've been finding using webinars etc to get across complex information. I can transmit difficult ideas really quickly with the right pictures, but it's MUCH harder with text. The feedback makes it clear that the visual transmittance of complex data is much more effective, and certainly more welcome. Problems in the use of language Message that people are getting from government is markets/heating/economics - no mention of climate - people are confused with the mixed message from government While there are advantages of doing digital activities - older audiences more difficult - have to do via children or younger relatives

<p>Holistic Approach</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bring the adaptation conversation down to a very local level • Climate is direct impact on livelihood - long term needs are more basic rather than essential - issues of deprivation and poverty - address political agency and vulnerability - shifting from a pathway to responding to immediate risk - some communities don't have the information needed to adapt • Many community members will go above and beyond and fill in where the state agencies cannot support - because of a bond formed within the community group • Consider approaches on Human adaptation from anthropology like work of Rivera Collazo in Caribbean and other parts of the world 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulties when projects take too long - may need much quicker follow up
<p>Resources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the funding wisely - and funds for on the ground engagement • Bring in tools and approaches to talk about loss and potentially parts that can be avoided - see work Scotland's Coastal Archaeology and the Problem of Erosion (SCAPE) Trust and tools like Rapid Coastal Zone Assessment Surveys (RCZAS) developed by Historic England • Community plans being developed in NI - giving adaptation a focus - 30 year plan. Regular surveys, questionnaires. • Climate - Building climate resilience in cultural heritage - using peoples experience of past events (understand risks and reactions), developed GIS tools for information exchange>> CLANDAGE project (Building Climate Resilience through Communities, Landscapes and Cultural Heritage project)-legacy and social history use, landscape changes mapped 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the limitations (environmental designations) state agencies was a massive learning curve and who can do what for you as a community group • Form a formal entity if in Ireland - funding sources will be minimal without it - the governance guidelines associated with reporting from and running companies and charities is really useful for group cohesion. But the state should make it easier and less expensive to form a company.

Appendix 5: Summary of WS2-Task 1 results: What actions/resources/guidance have you used with, or as part of communities which helped support PBA

Theme	Action/Resource/Guidance
Communication and Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal staff workshop for all council service areas to identify local risks • Workshops to plan natural and built environments - Geodesign Mulranny - Community futures programme https://mulrannygeodesignworkshop.wordpress.com/ • Engaging with experts - provided knowledge and advice • Stakeholder and power mapping is missing in existing resources - helps to be more inclusive in approach - Use neighborhood planning as tool • Informed communication at all levels • Model building instead of language - start with good and work backwards on what we need to do to get there • Local stories - make these part of the communication tools so it drives the point home - human centered approach - Mapping and talking about the lived experience • Pictures and visual cues are much better • In person can be much easier - bringing out more creative ways to express these things • Organise events inviting the community to climate adaptation activities (e.g. marram planting) and communicate the impacts of climate change • Online and personal surveys - used in funding applications - in engagement with local authorities to make a case for infrastructure to provide sustainable visitor infrastructure as a means of protecting the dunes from foot/vehicular traffic (Mahrees Conservation Group) • Asking people what they need rather than coming in with assumption about is needed - pre consultation consultation to find out key people and what their needs are • Need a variety of engagement methods available - think about accessibility • Link climate change adaptation benefits to socioeconomic benefits • Social media helps - if you're doing something that annoys people you'll know about it quick, if you don't hear often means they are fine with what you're doing • Reps of community groups - special amenity group - what are key issues to address and put in operational plan with key action owners - ownership lies with community but council facilitates it - community gets budget. They have to reach consensus amongst themselves - town improvements - not sure if could call it CCA plan - they may not know enough about adaptation • HA - covering lots of different communities, set ups different in every one, needing to know the players and taking their lead - found works in past is not having one set plan but the community being involved at start and flexibility in different • Public realm plans - get people to attend workshops and identify key issues - no preconceived notion - just saying we want to improve public realm - what do you think the key issues are? Give everyone three post it notes to select three main issues - similar issues appear - out of 20 issues that may be raised, then clear 5 repeated by many - work your way through • If you have a short time span you may only be able to engage with the "low-hanging fruit", if you have more time you can develop a strategy for the hard to reach • Climate Outreach people profiles - demographic, political learnings affect how people engage with what you're doing • Talks with key ppl - community council and asking about dynamics - identify those who are interested, (eg those already active such as leading Beach cleans) - identifying those key people - need at least a month get on community council agenda - lead in time • Get creative - to get input from all and not just committee literate - need to know when to not take the lead - success dependent on true representation of community -working with ppl in their own space • Knowing relationships between community members (and policy makers) is always an advantage - involves speaking to those locally - establishing what the situation is even before you start. Understand what's been done previously. Need to be aware of potential risks of engagement fatigue . Be sensitive to what's happened in area. Find out lessons learnt from past experiences. • Listening to community members, following through on what you say you'll do builds trust and relationships • Need to build trust to actually get people to be involved - give and take of ideas and insights • National flood forum - you need to give time for people to tell their stories - build a relationship and allow them the time they need to get the whole picture • Local power dynamics to be aware of it - local facilitators might be good to have • Community resilience structures and planning and partnerships - key officers who communities have a trusted relationship with

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highlight donut economics - thriving community rather than constant growth- Example of trees growing and then thriving • Campaigning was important - used community surveys to build support for action to conserve the sand dunes - helped develop a visitor management approach • Approaches are working - roads are able to stay open • Work with press to highlight the issues/ Present at any events/ workshops we're invited to • OPW Flood risk maps - a very potent message all on their own! • talk about climate in the framework of the SDGs
Collaboration and Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify connections and experts that can help - e.g. botanists - academic input was valuable for the Maharees Conservation Group • NPWS guidance - trying to translate it into something acceptable-Education • Linking in with existing networks, .e.g. PPN, older age groups, env. awareness offers. Developing networks to try and reach everybody. • Listening and relationship building at a community level as been really important - will now take actions together that we wouldn't have considered doing 4 years ago • We're all volunteers - getting people to work together to do things that they wouldn't have done before. • Market Research - Visitors and residents perceptions of relative importance of issues, levels of support for activities: Academic/ State Agency/ NGO input: NUI Galway Geography Dept (Dr Eugene Farrell); MTU Wildlife Biology (Dr Therese Higgins). NPWS/ Bird watch Ireland - Using their resources or advice in our activities or to create our own material • Clean Coasts - showed us how to plant marram grass and introduced us to people of help/influence • encourage people to sign up to EU Climate Pact and Climate Reality Leadership Corp • Looking at best practice from other places and seeing if/how we can apply these ideas here • Using maps and co-creating maps together - use past examples and what the future place will look like • Joesph roundtree foundation - EA forced to work with local flood groups - and they learned from them • Need to increase capacity within relevant agencies that will increase capacities in the community • Learn from other sectors on how to interpret things • Group collaging session - need people to respond - art can work well - don't need any overabundance of technical information • A lot of community groups are very knowledgeable but they need examples of what has worked elsewhere - they only trusted their knowledge up to a point • Involve the community from the start - collingswood greenway - partnerships are an asset • Climate NI - project where CNI supported local govt created toolkit - based on 5 different steps online and accessible for everybody - takes you through diff steps. First three steps are on development and last two steps are being finalised, Derry and Strabane Council. • Derry created their adaptation plan based on toolkit
Resource	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help people access specific funding pots • Resources need to be made accessible - online -training needs to be provided • Need to be mindful of the barriers the community faces - Need to be smart about how resources are to be used - going to have coffee can be the first step.
Motivation and Sustained involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Don't beat yourself up if you don't get everybody - not all care or want to be involved - if you get a few segments that means you're doing well. • Community can design and lead the climate sessions themselves and have ownership • Citizen science - e.g. condition surveys/monitoring change - by engaging people more directly with monitoring helps them understand risk and loss (applications from nature/culture) and helps to change behaviour/attitudes • Community archaeology - training people to become advocates themselves. Look at Citizen ShoreDIG for examples • Giving people control in adaptation - Marram grass planting • Follow Up - not one step and walk away - long term involvement • Local food growing - a focus for community resilience - there are connections in with adaptation in terms of growing food, building stronger communities - Sustainable Food Places is a good route to focus on a good food network which incorporates food and climate change • local food movement/networks are good focal point (Eatthestreets) • ACORN program • The message needs to come from the community • Build understanding about what is acceptable from a nature conservation and community perspective • Use historic landscapes maps (digital and physical) and heritage as a tool for distilling values across time that matter for people to encourage protective behaviours- behavioural change

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| | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The governance code - for guidelines - having a democratic and transparent process for organizing• Involve cultural presenters and the social science aspect of engagement• Younger groups - SDGs - Future generations and bringing the climate narrative into it |
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Appendix 6: Summary of WS2-Task 2 results - Maturity mapping of activities for community involvement

Level 1 - Beginning	Level 2 - Intermediate	Level 3 - Robust	Level 4 - Optimising
Never waste a crisis. Crisis events can get action kick started	Mitigation and adaptation – understand co-benefits, highlights NBS for carbon storage and flood alleviation examples	Supporting other groups - knowledge sharing networks	Co-operative model between both LAs and communities - Portrane IRL local community built it
Manage expectations at the start.	Showcase things that are already published	Identify and engage with existing structures	Strong communication and honesty
Reaching out and trying to find the gate keepers - making sure it's not the same voices all of the time. Find out how to reach out to children, farming community etc.	CCAT funded by Nat Resource Wales, has SMP in place, have actions more likely to take if there are other hooks e.g. if community select something that fits with different policy - steer them to that to options already supported by LA or funders. E.G. encouraged NBS in cards, bring into conversation	Council/ government is in the background and the local champion is driving change	To leverage money - need national hook – e.g. Ireland policy to buy out houses at coast, that's how we can get money, when there's no policy or precedent to do it's very hard.
Setting up as an official community group – with formal status was key to get recognition and taken seriously	Communicating to /with communities what is actually happening – clearly	Learning from peer relationships and networks - previous good practise - and apply it to you	For small scale projects - communities and local authorities may be able to lead but massive projects need to be led nationally to be able to fund it
Need to acknowledge that change takes time - it is going to take a while, need to be patient	The success that we has built confidence, credibility and funding to do more	Need granular level data and information	Continual evaluation on what is working and what isn't
Identify gatekeepers-levels of activity locally	Consultation results to help identify what people care about - link outputs. Sometimes gets missed about how to link different projects	Need to consider across scales - processes work differently in urban as compared to rural places	Encouraging disruptive innovation
Careful to build relationships - not deliberately embarrass e.g. the local authority.	Developing decision making to local government - but govt money is required - run in to govt budget problems -run into CBA or accounting issues - challenge- if govt money is required, and don't meet requirements of expenditure that actions can't be funded - need to look ahead and ensure resourcing can happen to respond to engagement	In urban areas you may have more issues around building a sense of place and community	Help communities become aware of other funding opportunities separate from the local authority / central Govt
Provide a reason /a motivation/ show a case study of others/ bring a speaker from a similar scenario/ to motivate formation of a group/ take action as a group - crisis? future impact depictions? Showing that action can be taken - give people hope to go on/ take action/ to develop resilience	Think about what comes next - succession planning	Joint funding applications for extra resources	Multi actor action at large scale - meaningful change
The process can be slow for a lot of reasons - it might need to be for good reasons - don't want to make the wrong decision and cause damage	Fingal council did INTERREG project on to educate people on the coast - ppl then become proud to find out the coast is special designated areas - makes them think / feel they are special - pride of place- helps tell story - there will be changes here, how does it affect the, and what does it mean	Policy at national level doesn't deliver equally across - important for policies to be filtered - place based policy - depending on places and highest risks, e.g. CARO groups responding to different risks - this can inform policy prioritisation - community become part of that decision	Trust and respect established at many / all levels between stakeholders

Take the pulse - community authored vision and plan and how to reach out to all parts of the community	Community members give solutions before being 'told'	Need networks to build wider capacity	Continuous support from central Government
Form a legal entity for funding/ credibility	Understand what is important to community - the key things that they are proud about and use that as way in.	Not just communities, need to talk about places and how communities relate to places - why it's important - both people and places in PBA play role - even when introducing NBS, relate to why you're doing it in this place - sometimes start place important	Mechanisms like natures early warning systems alongside MET climate data and the ownership of the former falls with community
Capability planning - work backwards from your vision - collective visioning	Do small project that is high enough profile to build trust	Building standards, land management, planning decisions all influence local action effectively and appropriately	Be less reactive - climate proof in advance - sit down with different planning/development groups in government
Learn from historic adaptation - older buildings are much more resilient than modern buildings	Consistency	Responsible local businesses with a big community investment ethic (local sourcing etc)	Use the opportunity for change
Inform on risks people may not be aware of- heat risks etc	By opening the spaces and allowing people to be involved people can be made aware of resources they already have	Local ownership - less bureaucracy , need practical support from LA but minimise red tape	Local knowledge is valued equally to scientific data and is used in decision-making - MAPS ARE A GOOD WAY OF DOING THIS
Make people aware of co-benefits - money/politics etc	Land management and land use - back to a more common sense approach - climate stories of lived experience to live from the past - policy hooks and co-benefits	Insurance issues - local groups liability that shouldn't be case	Use the pandemic as an opportunity to capitalise on the responses - it can be done - it needs to be done for climate
Community led adaptation right away is best	Go out to where the people are - go to groups that don't necessarily have a connection to climate - sure start /council of commerce	Getting NBS and adaptation principles incorporated within national policy - needs to be considered feasible	Learn and pass that learning on - storytelling being more prominent - make the lived experiences (intergenerational) and transboundary available
Clearly define adaptation - separate from mitigation	Acknowledge volunteerism - need to give credit to people		Need to be a solid presence in the communities - maintain partnerships and relationships - multi level and multi-actor
Education in community/across council departments etc - consequences and benefits that people don't see - well-being, creation of parks etc - multi-layered benefits	Clear simple language throughout		Create community climate champions that are embedded in the community
Value is integrated in how we speak about place - eg those who live their longer had a lot more interested - even when people leave they may be still be interested in	Sit down and get the entire story out of people - you can come at it for their issues		Sustained resource and time invested to keep momentum going
Place isn't always physical - it relates to anyone who has connection to area, not just those who live there, but ppl self-define connection to place - connection links to value	Building trust is essential		Community involvement would be resourced - find a way of making progress before a crisis - responsive not reactive

Engaging with young people - scouts etc. . Gap in awareness between younger and older generations. Older ppl interchange terms of environment and climate change and mitigation and adaptation much more. Need to steer conversations more with older groups whereas younger groups 'get it' more. Whereas adults used workshops to vent a lot about other topics - need to be quite strong facilitator	The whole adaptation journey - you need to tailor the evidence to the audience		Self-sustaining process - keeps improving and bringing more people into the group
Create safe space, open to learning	Knee-jerk reactions from climate can cause maladaptation - make sure this doesn't happen		Constant cycles of projects and iterations
Pilot projects and learn from - get feedback	Managing expectations is important - not every place can be saved - key is to communicate on a Clear, Honest, Accessible and Transparent basis on this and prepare those community members who will lose homes/ places and prepare for adaptation e.g. relocation where necessary		How to develop a self-sustaining community network that continues to be strong over time
Community members can feel helpless to CC issues	Become a knowledge sharing group - support other groups. Create a wider network		
Responsibilities - big ticket items not always able to do at community level	How to involve others and pick up others along the way		
Mitigation and adaptation - lack of understanding amongst community members - helping them understand differences	Need to create space to be reflective - look in to the past to create the future		
Manage expectations - say some of the actions may not be possible for now, but could be reviewed next time	Connecting people		
Highlight risks - can catalyse wider climate action	Many need a strong vision - sometimes you have to create a vision and this takes time		
	Develop democratic processes		
	All groups reflected - credible; legitimate		
	Find a way to motivate community - how to have a positive/negative image		

	Identify and recognise structures		
	Getting governance right - representation from across interests - surfers, farmers etc. credible, trustworthy people who can connect		
	Visioning and community planning started in Maharees		
	Stakeholder mapping at higher level - not accurate enough at local level - granular scales add to the overall picture - Map out your sphere of influence and who needs to be involved where and when		